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PSMF1 and PSMD8 are silenced in Alzheimer's Disease.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We studied pluripotent stem cell models of Alzheimer's Disease for discovery of proteasome-specific UPS (ubiquitin proteasome pathway) therapeutic targets to enhance amyloid clearance and/or halt cellular degeneration phenotypes. We describe here identification of PSMF1 and PSMD8 as candidate therapeutic targets in AD.